

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

METHODICAL SYSTEM OF TEACHING THE SPECIFIED TOPICS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SUB-STANDARDS FOR THE "FUNCTIONS" EDUCATIONAL UNIT (X CLASS).

Ibrahimov Firadun Nadir,

Sheki branch of ADPU,

doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor

https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0775-1048

Karimova Sevinj Ilgar

Teacher of the Department of Natural

Sciences and their Teaching Technology

of the Sheki branch of ADPU

Abstract

In the article, the content of the skills intended to become the subjects of the students in the process of realizing the materials for the "Functions" educational unit, which is included in the content of the Mathematics subject in the X classes of general education schools, is presented. Attention is focused on the place of the content elements that perform the "enabling function" in the formation of the mentioned skills in the "Functions" educational unit and the technology of turning them into actions in the students' cognition. Functions are considered appropriate to make it into a system as the transformed elements in teaching unit on the topics of "Functions and their giving ways", "Function and its giving methods", "Definition domain and set of values of some functions", "Properties of functions", "Even function, single function", "Partial functions", " $y = x^n, n \in N$ power functions", "Classification of functions", "Transformation of graphs", "Operations on functions", "Complex function", "Inverse function". It should be noted that the task system, which serves as a means of organizing and managing the educational process for mastering the content elements presented by the students, should contain verbs that are required to be performed in the topics. Examples of tasks of that kind are included in the content of the work."

Keywords. Teaching unit; content elements; topic; complex function; inverse function; power function; classification; transformation; vehicle; capacity building; assignment; organization and management of the educational process; methodical system.

The actuality of the subject. There are many recommendations that are useful to be adopted for guidance in the teacher's activity in the textbook complex and various educational literature about the teaching units, basic standards, sub-standards, and defined topics in the subject of mathematics. This is very useful in terms of organizing and managing the process of teaching mathematics according to the curriculum model. It is not denied that the continuous improvement of the teaching process in the subject is a logical, eternal problem. Of course, as the experience of using the curriculum is formed, the methodical system of the teaching process adequate to it should be improved. Based on this logic, we claim the relevance of the research of the topic "Methodical system of teaching the specified topics for the realization of the sub-standards for the "Functions" educational unit (Class X).

Interpretation of the summation of research materials. The analysis of the materials obtained from scientific sources provides a basis for such a generalization that in the content of mathematical subjects taught in general education schools, the materials related to the concepts of number, function and space have had a superior "enabling function" and along the line of development of these concepts (from simple to complex) brought together in a dialectical unity. Even many pedagogues (didactics, methodists) who have acquired the image of "classical status" have

supported such an idea that general mathematical education should refer directly (in some cases directly) to the development trend and level of existing mathematical science, as well as to the logic of the development of the concepts of numbers and functions. should be adequate. [5-8; 13]. The content lines of the Mathematics subject based on the curriculum model currently applied in general education schools are precisely the modernization of this idea.[2; 57]

Our generalization, derived from the research materials we collected on the mathematics subject curriculum, is that in the process of teaching the topics covered in the "Functions" educational unit, it is intended that students become subjects of the following skills:

- ◊ determines in various ways whether the dependence between two variables is a function;
- ◊ knows different ways of giving the function and applies it to problem solving;
- ◊ determines the domain of the function and the set of values;
- ◊ applies some methods of finding the domain of a function and the set of values analytically to given functions;
- ◊ defines the zeros of the function;
- ◊ determines the increment and decrement intervals of the function;
- ◊ determines the extrema of the function;

- ◊ determines whether a function is odd, even, or neither odd nor even;
- ◊ piecewise calculates the values of the given function;
- ◊ writes the formula of the given function in parts, constructs its graph;
- ◊ graphs the integral part function;
- ◊ models problems related to real-life situations with a given function;
- ◊ constructs graphs of power functions of even and odd degrees;
- ◊ apply the properties of power functions from even and odd degrees;
- ◊ constructs the graph of the main function (parent function) of the family of functions, shows its properties;
- ◊ defines the family to which the given function belongs, shows its properties;
- ◊ models a real-life situation with a function and presents its properties according to the family to which the function belongs;
- ◊ presents parallel transfer of graphs of functions graphically, analytical formula, verbally;
- ◊ presents the reflection of the graphs of the function graphically, analytical formula, verbally;
- ◊ writes new functions by performing operations on given functions;
- ◊ defines the properties of the new function;
- ◊ writes the composition of functions for two given functions;
- ◊ writes the formula of the complex function according to the given functions;
- ◊ calculates the values of a complex function;
- ◊ writes the formula of the function that is the inverse of the given function f using reciprocal operations; f^{-1}
- ◊ checks whether the function is an inverse function according to the given table of values, graph;
- ◊ according to the formulas of two given functions, determines whether they are mutually inverse functions;
- ◊ defines the domain of the inverse function;
- ◊ draws the graph of the inverse function.[3-4]

Mastering the materials of this educational unit will increase students' active mathematical vocabulary in the following concepts - function, domain, set of values, pair of values, dependence map, table of values, graph of a function, zeros of a function, increase and decrease of a function, extrema of a function, maximum and minimum of a function, symmetry of the graph of a function, partial function, integral function, stepwise graph, n-order parabola, family of functions, basic function, asymptote, parallel displacement of graphs, reflection of graphs, stretching and compression of graphs, addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of functions, complex function, composition of functions, rotating function, inverse function, mutual inverse functions and allows to be enriched with considerations related to them. [8;217]

It is recommended to take advantage of virtual tools (important links for teaching the course) and various worksheets as an additional resource in teaching the materials of the mentioned educational

unit. For the sake of justice, it should be said that it is possible to obtain examples of tasks of the mentioned nature from scientific sources produced by educational scientists of Azerbaijan and other nationalities (the presented list of literature can be selected as an address for this purpose).

Now let's give an interpretation of the generalizations on the topics presented above. First, let's start with "The function and its methods, domain of some functions and set of values". In our opinion, it is enough to devote 3 hours to teaching the subject. In the 1st hour, the main focus is on forming the ability to determine whether the dependence between two variables is a function. Students' knowledge of the function is summarized. The function is defined as a matching, and prevention rules. The main goal of this process should be for every student to come to the conclusion that "the rule that opposes a certain element x of the set X to each element y of the set Y is called a function defined in the set X ". It should be clear to them that multiple values against one value or multiple values against multiple values are not functions. Students should learn their marking $D(f)$ and $E(f)$. They should know that it is possible to determine whether the dependence between two quantities is a function or not according to the dependence map, the table of values and the graph of the function. In order to develop these skills, the teacher should take advantage of various task examples. Here, using worksheets can increase work efficiency.

In subsequent exercises (within 2 hours), attention is paid to the methods of assigning the function. Work aimed at forming the skills of students to transfer the function given in a certain form to other forms is being carried out. For this purpose, it is useful to perform skill-building tasks such as compiling a table of values of a given function in a graphical form, constructing a dependency map, expressing it analytically, and writing it in words. Due to dependence maps, it is recommended to pay attention to the tasks of determining the formula of the function according to the table. [9; 6-8]

In the process of teaching the subject, students should be involved in activities that form the basis for the formation of the skills of determining the domain of a function and the set of values. It should be clear to students that when giving a function, the domain may be restricted to a certain range of values, and this restriction may vary depending on the situation. It should be explained to them that there are many cases where functions are not defined in certain values of the argument (that is, these values are not included in its definition area).

It is necessary to bring to the students' attention that if the function is given by a graph, by projecting the points on the graph onto the axis x and the axis y , the domain of the function and the set of values can be found. At this time, care should be taken to mark the end points of the graph according to the given definition area.

Here, we know that it is necessary to emphasize that the work sheet has its own place in the "Mathematics-10" teacher's help book, which was

prepared as a methodical tool and tasks in the "Mathematics-10" textbook, which will contribute to the organization of effective training related to finding the domain of the function and the set of values. It is recommended that the future teacher who wants to learn the subject of RTM should become familiar with the mentioned textbook and methodical materials. It should be noted that there are also other methodical tools that benefit the activities of teachers working in secondary schools and the preparation of students (who are studying at the bachelor's level with the aim of becoming teachers in the future), as emphasized above, which have been operating in higher education institutions for a long time. developed by prominent scientists[10; 258-279].

Let's argue our opinion with examples of tasks taken from these sources and, by the way, let's draw attention to the fact that in this resource, the examples of tasks found in those sources have been used as much as possible. Our goal is to make students who use the tool more adequately prepared for the philosophy of general mathematical education.

Task. Find the domain of the function:

$$a) y = x^2 - 7x + 10;$$

$$b) f(x) = x + \frac{1}{x} \quad c) y = x^2 + x^{-2} \quad d) f(x) = \frac{3x - 9}{x^2 - x - 2}$$

$$e) f(x) = \frac{\sqrt{2-x}}{x-1}; \quad f) \frac{\sqrt{3x-x^2}}{\sqrt{x-1}} \quad g) y = \sqrt{\frac{3x-x^2}{x-1}}$$

Task. Show the set of values of the function:

$$a) y = 4 - x^2;$$

$$b) y = \sqrt{16 - x^2};$$

$$c) y = \sqrt{16 + x^2};$$

$$d) y = \sqrt{x^2 - 2x + 2}.$$

And so on. [3-4]

To the interpretation of generalization "Properties of functions. Let's continue on the topic "Double function, single function". It is enough to devote 2 hours to teaching the subject. First, educational work on forming students' skills on determining the zeros of the function is carried out. For this purpose, discussions are held regarding the intersection points of the axes x and y of the graph of the selected function. It should be clear to the students that the zeros of the function f mean points with coordinates $(a;0)$ on the graph, that is, the zeros of the function are the values of the argument that make the value of the function zero. It is possible to meet cases where the function has one or more zeros, and sometimes none. The zeros of the function divide its domain into several intervals, and the function keeps its sign constant in these intervals.

The next stage in teaching the subject is related to determining the intervals of increase and decrease of the function. Students should know that a function is increasing in a given interval $x_2 > x_1$ when any value of the argument that satisfies the condition taken from this interval satisfies the condition of corresponding values of the function $f(x_2) > f(x_1)$. If the argument is taken from the given interval $x_1 < x_2$ and has values $x_2 > x_1$, and $f(x_2) < f(x_1)$ the function $f(x)$ is decreasing in this interval. [3;14-19]

The process of teaching the subject is continued by engaging students in the tasks of determining the increase and decrease of linear and quadratic functions according to the graph. It should be explained to the students that the turning points correspond to the maximum and minimum of the function. If at the turning point the increase turns to decrease, this point is the maximum of the function, and if the decrease turns to increase, then this point is the minimum of the function.

In the process of teaching this topic, students get acquainted with both graphical and analytical ways of determining the single or double function. They learn that the graphs of odd functions are coordinate rather than the graphs of even functions y is symmetric about the origin. The graph of the function is neither an axis nor a coordinate y if it is not symmetric with respect to its origin, then that function is neither odd nor even function. [9; 12]

For example, function $g(x) = x^3 - x$ is odd, function $p(x) = x^2 + 2$ is even,

$$f(x) = |5 - 3x| \text{ function is neither odd nor even.}$$

It can be brought to the students' attention that the function $f(x) \equiv 0$ is both an even and an odd function, because the graph of the function $f(x) \equiv 0$ is symmetric with respect to both the axis y and the coordinate origin. In teaching the subject, it is useful for students to understand that functions in the form $f(x) = x^{2k}$ are even functions, and functions in the form $f(x) = x^{2k+1}$ are single functions. They should be able to understand that functions are often neither odd nor even functions if the formula of a function has both an even degree and an odd term, or if the formula has at least one odd degree term and a constant term. It would not be bad for students to observe that if an even function is increasing (decreasing) to the left of the axis of symmetry, then it is decreasing (increasing) to the right of the axis of symmetry. The application of the following content and required tasks is useful in teaching the subject:

Task. Determine the zeros of the function:

$$a) f(x) = \frac{1}{4}x - 3; \quad b) g(x) = \sqrt{5 - x^2};$$

$$; \quad c) h(z) = \frac{2z-5}{z+2} \quad d) q(n) = n^3 - 2n^2 - 3n$$

e) Graph any function whose zeros are numbers. 1) $-1; 3$; 2) $-2; 1; 4$

Task. Determine the intervals of increase and decrease of the function:

$$a) f(x) = x^2 - 2;$$

$$b) f(x) = x^3 -$$

$$2x; \quad c) t(x) = 2 - \frac{1}{x}; \quad d) y = \frac{2}{x-1};$$

e) Describe the graph of any increasing (decreasing) function with domain $[1;4]$.

f) $y = f(x)$ is a decreasing function defined in the range of $(-\infty; +\infty)$

Arrange the values of the function in ascending order:

$$a) f(0), f(4), f(2); \quad b) f(1), f(-1), f(3);$$

$$c) f(-\sqrt{3}), f(-2), f(\sqrt{2});$$

j) Find the zeros of the function, describe its graph schematically, indicate the sign stability intervals, increase-decrease intervals, write its extrema:

$$a) y = x^2 - 4; \quad b) y = |x| - 1; \quad c) y = -x^2 + 2x + 3.$$

Task. Identify the odd and even of the function:

1. a) $y = x^2 - 2x + 4$; b) $y = (x - 4)^2 - 3$ c) $y = -\frac{1}{2}x - 1$; d) $y = \frac{2}{x} - 1$;

e) $f(x) = x(x^3 + 2x)$; f) $y = \frac{|x|}{x^2 + 1}$

2. The function $f(x)$ assigned to the entire number axis is given. Find:

a) $f(x)$ pair function and if, $f(-4) = 7$ find the value of $f(4)$

b) $f(x)$ single function and, if so, $f(-4) = 7$ find $f(4)$

c) $f(x)$ if it is an even function and, the sum; $f(-3) = 8, f(5) = -2$ find $f(2) + f(5)$

ç) $f(x)$ singular function and if, the sum of $f(-2) = 3, f(4) = -7$ find $f(2) + f(0) + f(4)$

3. Can a function whose domain is an interval be odd or even??

a) $[-6; 6]$; b) $(-6; 6)$; c) $(-6; 6]$;

d) $[-9; 10)$; e) $(-\infty; 1) \cup (1; +\infty)$

and so on.

$[8; 220]$

Continuing our opinion on the topic "Partially given functions", we state that 1 hour is enough for the teaching of this topic. In the teaching of the subject, it is recommended that the process of familiarizing students with the concept of "partial functions" in the above-mentioned scientific-methodical sources [3-4;10] should be carried out in a form that has its own place below.

It is brought to the students' attention that in real-life situations, the dependencies between variable quantities are often expressed not by one, but by several formulas and inequalities. They are presented with a slide containing the solution to the problem with the content given below. The content of the slide is as follows:

The issue. The price of one shirt is 3 manats for those who buy at least 10 and at most 20 sports shirts in the wholesale store, and the price of one shirt is 2 manats for those who buy more than 20 shirts. Express the relationship between these two quantities by accepting the money received from the sale and the number of shirts sold. C_n

Solution: This situation can be expressed in the following general form with the functions $C(n)=3, 10 \leq n \leq 20$ and $C(n)=2 \cdot n, n > 20$

When $n = 15, n = 20, n = 30, n = 40$ find the values of the function $C(n)$

$n = 15 \vee n = 20$ the money obtained for paying the price condition $10 \leq n \leq 20$

we calculate with the formula $3n: C(15) = 3 \cdot 15 = 45; C(20) = 3 \cdot 20 = 60$

$n = 30 \vee n = 40$ according to the price condition: $n > 20$

$C(30) = 2 \cdot 30 = 60, C(40) = 2 \cdot 40 = 80.$

The presented preparatory process allows the following definition of a piecewise function: Functions given by different formulas in different intervals of the domain are called piecewise functions.

As is well known, a modular function is an example of a piecewise function, and students are familiar with the graph of a function $f(x) = |x|$. Taking advantage of this possibility, several graphs of

the modular function can be considered. Students should know that a piecewise function can also be linear, quadratic, etc. may include various expressions. It should be made clear to them that partial functions can also consist of constant functions. At this time, the graph of the function forms steps.

Students should gain experience in modeling various life situations with partially given functions and understand its analytical writing.

Experience shows that it is useful to involve students in the activity of mastering the features of the given functions and constructing graphs through various tasks, first with the close intervention of the teacher, and then by increasing their degree of independence.

The following can be an example for the first stage.

An example. Compute the values of the given piecewise function at the given values of the argument.

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 2x - 3, & x \leq 4 \\ 3x + 5, & x > 4 \end{cases} \quad a) x = 1,5; .b) x = -2$$

An example. Graph the given function piecewise. Investigate the continuity of the function according to its graph.

$$a) f(x) = \begin{cases} 4, & 0 \leq x < 2 \\ 5, & 2 \leq x < 4 \\ 6, & 4 \leq x < 6 \end{cases} \quad b) f(x) = \begin{cases} x + 1, & -3 \leq x < 1 \\ 3x - 1, & 1 \leq x \leq 3 \end{cases}$$

In the second stage, as we mentioned, it is advisable to continue the process of teaching the subject by organizing independent activities of students on learning tasks. Worksheets can be used for this purpose. [4]

" $y = x^n, n \in N$ " It is recommended to allocate 1 hour to the teaching of "power functions". It is advisable to start the teaching process by introducing students to the definition of the force function and presenting its general picture to students.

$n = 1, n = 2, n = 3$ Students have information on their cases, they can construct their graphs, they are familiar with their properties.

It should be clear to the students that the graph of the function $y = x^n$ is symmetric about the ordinate axis and similar to a parabola $y = x^2$ at any even value of n . The graph of the function at any singular value of n is symmetric with respect to the origin of the coordinate and is similar to a cubic parabola with the graph of at singular values greater than 1. [12; 166-170]

$n > 1, n \in N$ when the graph of the $y = x^n$ function is called a drawn parabola. $n > m$ the graph $y = x^n$ of the function in the interval $(0; 1)$ is located below the graph of the function $y = x^m$, and in the interval $(1; +\infty)$ above [3; 22]

The following content and required learning tasks may be acceptable in teaching the subject:

1. $x = 0; x = -3; x = 5$ compare the values of the functions at points with zero:

a) $f(x) = x^7; b) f(x) = x^6.$

2. $f(x) = x^3$ and $g(x) = x^4$ functions are given.

Compare: a) $f(0,1) \vee g(0,1); b) f(\frac{1}{2}) \vee g(\frac{1}{2});$

3. construct the graphs of the functions $y = x^4$ and $y = 16$ on the same coordinate plane and

indicate the points of intersection. Solve the inequalities according to the graphical representation $x^4 < 16$ and $x^4 > 16$.

2 hours can be devoted to the teaching of the topic "Classification of functions". The process of teaching the subject can be started by conducting discussions with the students around such a question: What functions have we learned so far?

The names and general images of the functions are said and sequentially recorded on the board: 1) Linear function: $y=kx+b$; 2) Fixed function: $y=c$; 3) Quadratic function: $y=x^2$; 4) Module function: $y=|x|$; 5) Power function: $y=x^n$; 6) Rational function: $y=1/x$; 7) Partial function: $y=[x]$. [11;24-28]

In teaching the subject, it is brought to the attention of the students that the functions included in the same family are obtained by different transformations of the basic function. In these two lessons, the main attention of the students is focused on writing the formula of the function according to the given situation and determining its main function, determining which family the function belongs to according to the graph, constructing the graph according to the given table of values, and determining the main function of the family.

In teaching this topic, it is recommended that the basic function table task be given as homework.

It is considered appropriate to spend 3 hours teaching the topic "Transformation of graphs". In the teaching of this topic, parallel transfer, reflection, stretching and compression of graphs are drawn into the center of attention. [3; 25-31]

Teaching about parallel transfer can be started by engaging students in practical activities as follows.

Practical work. 1) Mark the points $(0;0), (-1;1), (1;4)$ on the parabola $y=x^2$.

2) Move these points parallel to the vector $(4;1)$.

$(0;0) \rightarrow (4;1), (-1;1) \rightarrow (3;2), (2;4) \rightarrow (6;5)$.

3) Check whether the points obtained from the parallel transfer are located on the parabola

$$y=(x-4)^2+1.$$

After the implementation of such a practical work, the following information can be given to the students, and it is logical to hope that the students will be in great difficulty with this information.

In parallel translation, all the points of the graph move by the same distance in the given direction. The shape of the graph does not change. Let's move each point of the graph of the function $y=f(x)$ parallel to the vector $(m;n)$: $A(a;b) \rightarrow A_1(a+m;b+n)$

When the coordinates of point A satisfy the equation $b=f(a)$, the coordinates of point A_1 satisfy the equation $y-n=f(x-m)$. That is, when the graph of the function $y=f(x)$ is transferred parallel to the vector $(m;n)$, the graph of the function $y=f(x-m)+n$ is obtained: the given graph is in the horizontal direction $|m|$ unit (right if $m>0$, left if $m<0$), vertical direction $|n|$ is shifted one (up if $n>0$, down if $n<0$).

In the case of $n=0$, the graph is shifted parallel only in the horizontal direction and the new function $y=f(x-m)$ becomes. It is necessary that this information be visualized for all cases. A system of learning tasks should be used in order to turn the obtained information

into a functional component in the students' experience. The following content and form tasks can be included in this system:

* Construct the graphs of the given functions using the graph of the function $f(x)=\sqrt{x}$. Write each conversion in words.

a) $g(x)=\sqrt{x-3}$; b) $t(x)=\sqrt{x-2}$

* $y=f(x-m)+n$ was obtained by parallel displacement of the graph of the function $y=f(x)$ in horizontal and vertical directions.

a) Show by example that the order of transfer does not matter.

b) How do the values of the parameters m and n affect the domain of the function and the set of values?

*The function $f(x)=1/x$ is not defined at the point $x=0$, at which point is the function $f(x-3)$ not defined? Graph the functions $f(x)$ and $f(x-3)$ on the same coordinate plane, etc.

Refusal. At this stage, work is carried out in order for students to master the forms of presentation of graphs of functions graphically, with analytical formulas and in words. The students' attention is focused on the cases of reflection taking into account the ordinate axis, the abscissa axis and the coordinate origin.

The function that best demonstrates the transformation corresponding to reflection action on functions is the square root function. The function $y=\sqrt{x}$ also allows us to model many physical phenomena as a quadratic function. It is recommended that the teacher take this fact into account.

At this stage, you can use examples of tasks such as:

* Write the base function and transformations for each function.

a) $y=-x^2+2$; b) $y=-\sqrt{x}+1$; c) $y=\frac{1}{x-1}$; d) $y=1-\frac{1}{x}$.

* Plot the graphs of the functions for the given set of points of the graph

Determine which transformations of the functions $y=x$, $y=x^2$, $y=\sqrt{x}$, $y=x^3$ correspond to:

a) $\{(-2;8), (-1;1), (0;0), (1;-1), (2;-8)\}$;

b) $\{(0;0), (-1;1), (-4;2), (-9;3), (-16;4)\}$;

c) $\{(-2;-4), (-1;-1), (0;0), (1;-1), (2;-4)\}$;

d) $\{(-4;3), (-2;1), (0;-1), (2;-3), (4;-5)\}$ etc.

It is convenient to present the transformations of the function graphs contained in the topic "Stretching and compression of graphs" with the quadratic function and the modular function. It is better that this work is carried out in the form of a discussion with the students. It should be clear to the students that the abscissa of the point changes while the abscissa remains the same during stretching and compression from the abscissa axis.

$$(a;b) \rightarrow (a;l \cdot b)$$

If the point $a(a;b)$ is on the graph of the function $y=f(x)$, then $b=f(a)$. Then the point $A_1(a;l \cdot b)$ is the graph of the function $y=l \cdot f(x)$ by drawing the graph of $f(x)$ l times from the abscissa axis when $l > 1$, and $\frac{1}{l}$ times to the abscissa axis when $0 < l < 1$ is obtained by squeezing. In tension and compression from the ordinate axis, the ordinate of the point changes while the abscissa remains the same.

$$(a;b) \rightarrow (k \cdot a;b)$$

If the point $a(a;b)$ is on the graph of the function $y=f(x)$, then $b=f(a)$. Then the point $A_1(k \cdot a;b)$ is located on the graph of the function $y=f(\frac{x}{k})$. The graph of the function $y=f(\frac{x}{k})$ by drawing the graph of $f(x)$ from the ordinate axis k times when $k>1$,

When $0<k<1$, it is obtained by pressing the ordinate axis $\frac{1}{k}$ times. [3-4]

It is important to take advantage of the system of tasks in order to ensure that the highlighted items are mastered by the students. This system may include:

* Graph functions by base function.

$$a) y=2x^2; \quad b) y=2(x-1)^2; \quad c) y=3|x|;$$

$$d) y=-|3x|.$$

* Functions are derived from each other with certain transformations. Describe these transformations.

$$f(x)=\sqrt{x} \rightarrow g(x)=2\sqrt{x-2} \rightarrow h(x)=2\sqrt{x-2}+3 \rightarrow k(x)=-2\sqrt{x-2}-3$$

* Write down by which transformations the graph of each function is obtained from the graph of the given basic function $f(x)$.

$$1) f(x)=x \quad a) y=3x \quad b) y=-2x \quad c) y=\frac{1}{2}x+1$$

$$2) f(x)=x^2 \quad a) y=x^2+3 \quad b) y=(x-3)^2$$

$$c) y=2(x-1)^2+3$$

$$3) f(x)=\sqrt{x} \quad a) y=2\sqrt{x} \quad b) y=\sqrt{2x}$$

$$c) y=2\sqrt{x-1}+1$$

$$4) f(x)=\frac{1}{x} \quad a) y=\frac{2}{x}$$

$$b) \frac{1}{2x} \quad c) y=\frac{1}{x}-1 \text{ etc.}$$

It is considered appropriate to allocate 1 hour of time to the teaching of the topic "Operations on functions". In the process of teaching this subject, students should understand that a new function can be obtained by performing calculations on the given functions. The domain of the function obtained as a result of addition, subtraction, and multiplication performed on the functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ is the set of real numbers where both of these functions are defined. In other words, the domain of the new function is the intersection of the domain of the functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$:

$$D=D(f) \cap D(g) \quad [3; 32-33]$$

The ratio of the functions is determined for the values of the argument from the set D that make the function in the denominator different from zero. If the functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ are any function defined in a certain set of real numbers, addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division operations are performed on them according to the following rule:

$$(f+g)(x)=f(x)+g(x); \quad (f-g)(x)=f(x)-g(x);$$

$$(f \cdot g)(x)=f(x) \cdot g(x); \quad \left(\frac{f}{g}\right)(x)=\frac{f(x)}{g(x)}, \quad g(x) \neq 0.$$

The process of mastering the mentioned rules depends on the organization of purposeful activities of students on correctly selected tasks. Here you can benefit from the following task examples:

* Write the formulas of the functions $f+g$, $f-g$, $f \cdot g$, $\frac{f}{g}$ according to the given functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ and indicate the domain of determination.

* Construct the graph of the function $h(x)=(f+g)(x)$ according to the graphs of the functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$.

* Functions $f(x)=x$, $x \in [-1;9]$ and $g(x)=\sqrt{x}$, $x \in [0;16]$ are given.

Find the domain of the function $h(x)=(f+g)(x)$ and graph it by making a table of values.

* Given: $f(x)=2x$ and $g(x)=x^2$

a) Make a table of values of the function $(f \cdot g)(x)$.

b) Graph the function $h(x)=(f \cdot g)(x)$.

c) Determine the range and set of values of the function $h(x)$. and so on. [8; 225]

It is enough to devote 2 hours to teaching the topic "complex function". We need to emphasize that there is a special place for the task-type issues in mastering the concepts. This consideration can be applied to every concept contained in all content lines [1; 207-239]. In the "Mathematics-10" textbook, it is considered appropriate to start the process of familiarizing students with the concept of "complex function" by directing their attention to such a study.

The issue. The price of one liter of gasoline is 0.95 manat. Aykhani's car consumes 0.08 liters of gasoline per kilometer.

a) How can you calculate the money Aykhan spent for the gasoline spent on the 50 km journey? In how many steps can this calculation be performed?

b) Write the function $V(d)$ that shows the dependence of the consumed gasoline on the distance traveled.

c) Write the function $M(V)$ of the dependence of money spent on gasoline on its volume.

d) Write the function $M(d)$ that shows the money Aikhana spends on gasoline during the journey, using the functions in b) etc.). Here, the values of the argument are the values of which variable? [3; 34-35]

Such a study, of course, creates conditions for easy assimilation of the material presented below by students.

The teacher says that in many cases the values that a function's argument can take are determined by the values of another function. Suppose the functions f and g are given. Consider two situations.

The numbers x are included in the domain of the function g , and the numbers $g(x)$ are included in the domain of the function f . In this case, the function that opposes the number $f(g(x))$ to each number $x \in D(g)$ is called the complex function (composition) of the functions f and g and is written as $(f \circ g)(x)$:

$$(f \circ g)(x)=f(g(x)). \quad [9; 24-25]$$

The numbers x are included in the domain of the function f , and $f(x)$ are included in the domain of the function g . In this case, the composition of functions f and g is $(g \circ f)(x)$:

$$(g \circ f)(x)=g(f(x))$$

It is specially brought to the students' attention that the notations $(f \circ g)(x)$ and $(g \circ f)(x)$ (as well as the notations $f(g(x))$ and $g(f(x))$) denote two different complex functions. The composition $f(g(x))$ can be constructed if $E(G) \subset D(f)$, and the composition $g(f(x))$ can be constructed if $E(f) \subset D(g)$.

Students should deduce that the composition $f \circ g$ is obtained by writing $g(x)$ instead of the argument x in

the function $f(x)$. By the same rule, the composition $g \circ f$ is obtained by writing $f(x)$ instead of the argument x in the function $g(x)$.

By engaging students in activities on purposefully selected tasks, the concept of complex function is mastered perfectly. Such tasks include the following:

* Calculate according to the functions $f(x)=4x$, $g(x)=2x^2-1$ and $h(x)=x^2+1$.

a) $f(g(-1))$; b) $(h \circ (g \circ f))(\frac{1}{2})$; c) $(f \circ (g \circ h))(2)$.

* Determine the functions $f(g(x))$ and $g(f(x))$ given $f(x)$ and $g(x)$.

a) $f(x)=1-x^2$ and $g(x)=2x+5$; b) $f(x)=\sqrt{x-1}$ and $g(x)=x^2+2$;

c) $f(x)=x^2+3x+1$ and $g(x)=x+1$,

* If $f(x)=x^2-5$, $g(x)=\sqrt{x^2+1}$, solve the inequality $f(g(x))<0$. and so on.

It is enough to spend 2 hours teaching the topic "Inverse function". It is considered appropriate to begin the teaching of the subject with a discussion about the reciprocal operations between the four arithmetic operations.

It is emphasized that addition and subtraction, multiplication and division are mutually inverse operations. To algebraically define a function that is the inverse of a given function, the reciprocal of operations is used. Discussions are conducted on specially selected functions. For example, it is clarified that the function $f(x)=3x+2$ multiplies the variable by 3 and adds 2 to it. To get back to x from the function $f(x)$, reverse the operations (multiply x by 3 first and add 2 to it) (subtract 2 from x , divide the result by 3) and inverse of this function it is possible to get an analytical form of the function

In the process of teaching the subject, students should understand that for the existence of a function that is the inverse of the function f , each value in its domain must correspond to a value from the domain of values, such functions are called inverse functions. Otherwise, that is, if one value of x corresponds to more than one value of the function, it is not a reciprocal function, and there is no function with its inverse. Interrelationships of operations (addition and subtraction, multiplication and division) are used to algebraically define a function that is the inverse of a given function. To find the inverse function of the function given by the formula: 1) variable x from the given equation is expressed by y ; 2) in the obtained equation, y is written instead of x , and x is written instead of y . The function $x=f^{-1}(y)$ is called the inverse function of the function $y=f(x)$.

It is possible to determine whether a function is a rotating function or not with the help of a horizontal line according to its graph. If the horizontal line intersects the graph at more than one point, the function is not a rotary function and has no inverse function.

In general, functions that only increase or only decrease in the domain have inverses, such functions are inverse functions. Functions $f(x)=-x$, $f(x)=x^3$, $g(x)=\sqrt{x}$ can be examples of inverse functions. The domain and set of values of a function and its inverse are reversed. The graphs of the function and its inverse are symmetric about the straight line $y=x$. If the graph

of the function f is given, the graph of its inverse function can be obtained by symmetrically transforming it to the straight line $y=x$.

In order to master the above-mentioned by the students, such a system of tasks should be used that the verbs required to perform in them condition the mastery of the mentioned information. It would be useful to include tasks such as the following in this system.

* The function is given by the set of points: $\{(8;2);(1;1);(\frac{1}{8};\frac{1}{2});(-8;-2)\}$. Show the given correspondence and its inverse correspondence with the help of arrows.

* Construct a table corresponding to the inverse function of the function given by the table.

If $f(x)$ is a function with inverse and $f(1)=7; f(-3)=9; f(6)=2$, find the values of inverse function $f^{-1}(9)$, $f^{-1}(7)$, $f^{-1}(2)$.

* Write reciprocal inverse functions with the given functions. Are the given function and its inverse increasing or decreasing?

a) $y=2x$; b) $y=-4x+5$; c) $y=3x-14$;

d) $y=-\frac{2}{3}x$; d) $y=3x-3$

* Graph each given function and its reciprocal inverse on the same coordinate plane.

a) $f(x)=-2x+5$; b) $f(x)=x^2, x \geq 0$

* Graph the given functions. From the graph of each function, determine whether it has an inverse function.

a) $f(x)=x+3$; b) $f(x)=|x|+2$; c) $f(x)=2x^3$

* Write the formula of the reciprocal of the given function and the inverse function.

a) $f(x)=16x^4, x \leq 0$; b) $f(x)=\frac{4}{9}x^2, x \geq 0$; c) $f(x)=-8x^3$.

and so on.

At the end of the unit, it is useful to engage students in summarizing tasks. Examples of such tasks include:

* Find the domain of functions.

a) $f(x)=\sqrt{4x-2}$; b) $f(x)=\frac{4}{\sqrt{4x-2}}$; c) $f(x)=\frac{\sqrt{4-x^2}}{x-1}$

* Find the zeros of the functions.

a) $f(x)=4x+6$; b) $f(x)=\sqrt{x-1}-2$.

* Investigate the odd-even function.

a) $f(x)=(x-2)^2+(x+2)^2$;

b) $f(x)=x^2+(m-1)x+3, m=1; m=0$

* Graph the given function piecewise: $f(x)=\begin{cases} 2x, & x \geq 1 \\ -x+3, & x < 1 \end{cases}$

* The given functions are recursive functions. Write the inverse functions corresponding to these functions.

a) $f(x)=\frac{1}{2x-1}$; b) $f(x)=\frac{1-x}{x-2}$ and so on.

The authors of the "Mathematics 10" methodical manual recommended defining the criteria for the summative (small) assessment of students' mastery levels in the "Functions" educational unit in the following content:

1. Determines whether the dependency is a function or not.

2. Determines the properties of the function (range and range of values, zeros, increasing and decreasing intervals, extrema, odd or even).

3. Writes the formula of the given function in parts, constructs its graph, and calculates its values.

4. Constructs graphs of power functions of even or odd degree.

5. Presents the transformations of functions according to the main function graphically, analytically, and verbally.

6. Checks whether the function has an inverse function according to the given table of values, graph, and determines its formula analytically.

7. Writes a new function by performing actions on the given functions.

8. Writes the formula of the complex function according to the given functions and calculates its values. [4]

In our opinion, these presented criteria are correctly formulated to determine the level of realization of the enabling functions of the "Functions" educational unit.

The result. 1) In the process of teaching the topics covered in the "Functions" educational unit, the focus should be on the selection and application of types of tasks so that students become the subjects of the verbs based on the expected results;

2) In the process of teaching materials for the "Functions" educational unit, the inclusion of necessary terms in the content of students' active mathematical vocabulary should be considered as an important didactic requirement;

3) It is advisable to use virtual tools (important links for teaching the course) and various worksheets as an additional resource in teaching the materials of the "Functions" educational unit;

4) Since the materials of the "Functions" educational unit belong to the "Algebra and Functions" content line, in the real pedagogical process they are used both in full (with the content covered by the subject of Mathematics as a whole) and the parts related to each content line (subsystems of the other four content lines). dialectic unity between its elements ("system-structure" approach-"full-" relations) should be expected;

5) Expectation of the "opportunity - action - quality" paradigm in the selection and systematization of tasks has a positive effect on the efficiency of the educational process.

Literature

1. Adigozelov AS Theoretical foundations of mathematics education at school (Textbook). Baku: ADPU printing house, 2018.

2. Subject curricula for grades I-IV of general education schools. Baku: "Education, 2008.

3. Kahramanova N.M., Karimov MA, Huseynov I.H. "Mathematics-10" (Textbook). Baku: "Radius", 2017.

4. Kahramanova NM, Karimov MA, Huseynov I.H. "Mathematics-10" (Methodical tool for the teacher). Baku: "Radius", 2017.

5. Ibrahimov FN Methodology of teaching mathematics in general schools (Teaching materials). Baku: "Translator", 2015.

6. Ibrahimov FN Teaching technology of mathematics based on the curriculum model in secondary schools (Teaching materials). Baku: "Mutercim", 2016.

7. Ibrahimov FN Philosophy, didactics, implementation technology of mathematical education in secondary general education schools (Textbook). Baku: "Mutercim", 2018.

8. Ibrahimov FN Lectures on the methodology of teaching mathematics in secondary schools (Teaching materials). Baku: "Mutercim", 2019

9. Mardanov MC, Yagubov MH, Mirzayev SS and others Algebra and the beginning of analysis (textbook for the 10th grade of secondary schools). Baku: "Chashioglu", 2007.

10. Mammadov R. Higher mathematics. (Textbook for higher schools). Baku: "Turan House", 2013.

11. Nasibov MX Elements of mathematical analysis in the school course (methodical materials). Baku: "Maarif", 1991.

12. Kochetkov YS, Kochetkova Y.Ch. Algebra and elementary functions. Part I (Teaching manual for 9th grade students of secondary schools). Baku: "Maarif", 1973.

13. Kolyagin Yu. M., Lukankin G.L. Basic concepts in the school mathematics course. M., "Enlightenment", 1974.